

Development and reutilisation of a fertiliser-based culture medium for the commercial production of *Chlorella sorokiniana*

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Abstract

Microalgae-based processes represent an innovative productive approach in the context of the circular bioeconomy. However, challenges such as the optimisation of production processes need to be addressed for industrial-scale feasibility. In this work, a novel culture medium was developed and specifically designed for *Chlorella sorokiniana*, a strain with potential for human food consumption. A range of nitrogen sources were tested (nitrate, nitrite, ammonium and urea), with sodium nitrate yielding the fastest growth rate. The optimisation was done in bubble columns with controlled pH (8.0), temperature (25 °C), irradiance ($950 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and aeration (0.2 v/v/min). The nitrogen-to-phosphorus (N:P) molar ratio was then optimised (optimum=21) and further reductions in macro- and micro-nutrient levels showed no productivity decline, even with micronutrient levels reduced by up to 80%. The final optimised medium resulted in $1.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$, $0.12 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{HPO}_4$, $0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ MgSO}_4$, $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ CaCl}_2$ and $0.005 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ micronutrients commercial mixture, which produced approximately $4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ biomass at a rate of $0.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. Then, the exhausted culture medium was recirculated back into the system during semi-continuous cultivation to reduce both water and nutrient requirements. Biomass concentration decreased as the proportion of supernatant recirculation increased, from $3.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ without recirculation to $2.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ with 70% of supernatant recirculation. Measurements of turbidity, viscosity, total organic carbon and total aerobic mesophylls of the exhausted media highlighted the need for pre-treatment strategies to mitigate the effects of reusing the exhausted culture medium on growth. Future research will refine these strategies to balance cost-effectiveness, productivity, and sustainability in industrial microalgae production.

Keywords: biomass, sustainability, renewable resources, recirculation, photosynthesis

1. Introduction

Microalgae cultivation offers a promising solution to global challenges, including the need for sustainable energy production, ensuring food security, and promoting environmental sustainability ¹. Microalgae have a wide range of applications such as the production of biofuels, food, feed, and agricultural products as well as the treatment of wastewater and carbon sequestration ²⁻⁴. Among microalgae species, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, has been identified as a promising candidate for food production due to its biological properties ⁵⁻⁷. This microalga has a high capacity to accumulate substantial levels of essential amino acids, carbohydrates, fatty acids and chlorophyll derivatives, rendering it suitable for human consumption within the European Union. *C. sorokiniana* is excluded from the scope of the Novel Food Regulation as it has been consumed in a culinary context prior to 15 May 1997 ⁸. Furthermore, its rapid growth rate, adaptability to diverse environmental conditions, and high biomass productivity underscore its suitability for industrial-scale applications ⁹. However, the economic and environmental sustainability of microalgae production requires further improvement ¹⁰. Addressing these challenges involves optimising cultivation conditions and managing nutrient availability effectively. The cost and sustainability of culture media is a major barrier, as traditional formulations rely on expensive and non-renewable reagents. Optimising water and nutrient supply (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) is also essential for improving the feasibility of industrial microalgae production.

To achieve the most optimal growth conditions for the cultivation of *C. sorokiniana*, it is essential to maintain precise control over several key factors. These include the pH, temperature, light, and nutrient availability. Among the available nutrients, nitrogen and phosphorus have particular importance as macronutrients due to their significant influence on the yield and composition of biomass. At the industrial scale, agricultural fertilisers are the most common nutrient source. The main reasons are that they are available at large quantities and their cost. Wastewater is also used as a nutrient source;

however, this strategy does not allow using the biomass for high-value sectors such as the food industry. Nitrogen is essential for the biosynthesis of fundamental cellular components, including proteins, nucleic acids, and chlorophylls. It plays a crucial role in both growth and physiological activities of microalgae ¹¹. The type and concentration of nitrogen sources not only affect the growth of microalgae but also their biochemical composition ¹². Most microalgae assimilate nitrogen more easily when it is in its most reduced form. The order of preference for nitrogen utilisation is generally $\text{NH}_4^+ > \text{NO}_2^- > \text{NO}_3^-$ ¹³. Microalgae can also assimilate urea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$), an affordable nitrogen source with high percentage of nitrogen content. The metabolism of $\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$ releases ammonium (NH_4^+) and carbon dioxide (CO_2), whereas it also supports the accumulation of valuable components, as proteins, soluble sugars, and carotenoids ¹⁴. Optimising the form and availability of nitrogen is, therefore, a critical step in enhancing the productivity of *C. sorokiniana*. Similarly, phosphorus plays a vital role in several processes, including photosynthesis, energy transfer, and cellular signaling ¹⁵. The balance between nitrogen and phosphorus, often guided by the Redfield ratio (N:P = 16:1, molar ratio), influences growth dynamics. However, this ratio may not always be suitable for every species or cultivation system ¹⁶. Other important nutrients that need to be provided include CaCl_2 and MgSO_4 , as it plays a key role in the synthesis of chlorophyll molecules ¹⁷. Furthermore, the supply of a range of micronutrients, including metal ions (e.g., iron, calcium, magnesium) that are crucial for enzyme function, is essential ¹⁸.

Water is also a critical input in microalgae production systems. Producing 1 kg of biomass requires approximately 1600-2900 L of water ¹⁹. To reduce the water requirements, different strategies are being investigated such as the reutilisation of the exhausted medium that is the most widely applied. Other strategies such as production using wastewater are also effective, but the produced biomass cannot be used as food or in high-end markets. The recirculation strategy can also be used to reduce nutrient use as the residual nutrients that remain in the spent media are also reused. This practice also

reduces the need to dispose of nutrient-rich waters, thereby reducing the risk of environmental pollution. The effect of water reutilisation on the growth of microalgae has been shown to be strain dependent. While some studies demonstrated growth promotion^{20,21}, some others have observed negative effects either on growth or on the biochemical composition of the biomass^{21,22}.

The first aim of this study was to develop a cost-effective culture medium for the scalable production of *C. sorokiniana* and to assess the impact of nutrient reduction on biomass productivity. The strain used was isolated at the Cabo de Gata-Níjar National Park and has not been studied before. Additionally, a secondary aim was to evaluate the feasibility of cultivating *C. sorokiniana* using recirculated culture media, with a focus on enhancing sustainability by lowering both environmental impact and production expenses.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Microalga used

The microalga used in this study was *Chlorella sorokiniana*, isolated from Rambla de Morales (36.79518, -2.25833; Almeria, Spain) in March 2024. This microalga is therefore adapted to the environmental conditions of Almeria.

2.2. Culture medium composition and growth conditions

The experiments were performed at a laboratory scale using 0.3 L glass bubble columns with spherical bases (3 cm in diameter and 45 cm in height) that have been described elsewhere [NO_PRINTED_FORM]²³. These photobioreactors were equipped with monitored systems to control light intensity, pH and temperature, ensuring stable and reproducible culture conditions. The pH and temperature were maintained constant at 8.0 and 25 °C, respectively. The former was achieved by on-demand injection of carbon dioxide. Illumination was provided by fluorescent lamps using a 12:12 h light:dark period with an

average irradiance reaching the culture of $950 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Agitation was achieved by bubbling filtered air ($0.2 \mu\text{m}$) at a constant rate of 0.2 v/v/min . The air was passed through a 0.5 L Drechsel bottle containing autoclaved distilled water before entering the reactors to minimise water evaporation. The volume of the culture was controlled by adding distilled water before sampling.

Different culture media, listed in Table 1, were assessed. The culture media were prepared using agricultural-grade reagents (fertilisers) instead of analytical-grade chemicals to replicate cost-effective and industrially relevant conditions. The fertilisers were kindly provided by Biorizon Biotech (Almeria, Spain). Four initial media formulations (A, B, C, D) were developed to evaluate the efficiency of different nitrogen sources. These formulations maintained a constant N:P molar ratio of 16:1, which is the Redfield ratio and considered as the optimal for marine organisms ²⁴. Following these trials, media A6, A11, A16, and A21 were prepared to test varying N:P molar ratios from 6:1 to 21:1. Medium A and Medium A16 are the same, the name was changed for ease of comparison between this medium and A6, A11, and A21. Further modifications were made in subsequent formulations (A21-I to A21-VII) to reduce nutrient inputs progressively. This optimization included reductions of up to 75% in magnesium sulphate and calcium chloride concentrations, as well as over 80% reduction in the concentration of the commercial micronutrient mixture Karentol[®] Mix Super (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain), which contains boron, copper, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc.

The photobioreactors were inoculated with a standard culture at a concentration of approximately $3.0 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ prepared using $0.9 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ NaNO}_3$, $0.18 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $0.14 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{HPO}_4\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $0.015 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of a commercial micronutrient mixture. The reactors were inoculated to an initial concentration of approximately $0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. All the media were assessed in triplicate using three identical photobioreactors and being each photobioreactor the experimental unit. The biomass was harvested using a Sigma 3-18 KS centrifuge (Sigma Laborzentrifugen GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany) operating

at $8000 \times g$ for 10 min and autoclaved recipients. The harvested biomass was frozen, freeze-dried, vacuum-sealed, and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The exhausted culture media were either discarded, used for analytical determinations, or reused back in the system as described below.

2.3. Recirculation of the exhausted media

In this study, three recirculation rates (30, 50, and 70%) were tested to evaluate their impact on nutrient dynamics and microalgae growth. The experiment was conducted in two phases: an initial batch culture, followed by a semi-continuous culture. The batch culture was carried out as described above. At the end of the batch phase, the N-NO_3^- and P-PO_4^{3-} concentrations were below 2.0 and $0.5\text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively for all the treatments. Then, the reactors were operated in semi-continuous mode using a dilution rate of 0.3 day^{-1} , which means that every day 30% of the culture was replaced with fresh culture medium. The harvested culture was centrifuged using a Sigma 3-18 KS centrifuge (Sigma Laborzentrifugen GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany) operating at $8000 \times g$ for 10 min. The concentration of nutrients remaining in the supernatant was measured as described below. Nutrients and autoclaved distilled water were added to the supernatant (exhausted culture medium) to restore the initial levels. For example, the medium recirculated at a recirculation percentage of 30% contained 70% of autoclaved distilled water. The enriched supernatant was then used back in the system. The volume of the system was kept constant; evaporation was compensated using autoclaved distilled water. These trials were carried out in triplicate using three independent photobioreactors. The pH (8.0), temperature ($25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), irradiance ($950\text{ }\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and aeration (0.2 v/v/min) were controlled.

2.4. Analytical determinations

To evaluate the culture performance, biomass concentration and chlorophyll fluorescence ratio, F_v/F_m values were measured daily as described in a previous work

[NO_PRINTED_FORM] ²⁵. Briefly, the biomass concentration was calculated by dry weight, filtering 20 mL of the culture using 0.2 µm filters, washing the filter twice with the same amount of distilled water, and drying in an oven at 80 °C during 24 h. A calibration curve was done between the biomass concentration and the optical density measured at 680 nm using a Genesys™ 10S UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain). The optical density was measured daily twice per natural replicate. The carbon analyses were done using a HACH kits to determine total organic (TOC) and inorganic (TIC) carbon (LCK381; Hach Lange GmbH, Dusseldorf, Germany). Nutrient analysis for nitrate (N-NO₃⁻) and phosphate (P-PO₄³⁻) were conducted following the official standard methods established by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture as described elsewhere ²⁶. Briefly, the N-NO₃⁻ concentrations were measured spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 220 and 275 nm using a Genesys™ 10S UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) following the Nitrate Standard IC 74246 method. The P-PO₄³⁻ levels were quantified measuring absorbance at 430 nm, using a visible spectrophotometric technique based on the formation of a phospho-vanado-molybdate complex (Phosphate Standard for IC: 38364).

Besides the nutrient content, the turbidity, viscosity, and the bacterial concentration of the recirculated exhausted media (free of cells) were also assessed. Briefly, the turbidity was determined according to the ISO 7027 International Standard using an HI 93703 HANNA turbidity meter (Hanna Instruments, RI, USA). The viscosity was measured using an LVDV-II+ viscometer (Brookfield Engineering, MA, USA). Finally, the bacterial concentration was also determined. The plating medium employed was PCA (Plate Count Agar) and serial dilutions were performed in PBS (Phosphate Buffered Saline). The supernatant obtained during the semi-continuous growth phase was diluted to reduce the bacterial concentration to a countable range (30-300 ufc). A small aliquot of each dilution was then plated onto PCA agar plates and incubated at 35°C for 24 h. The

colonies were then counted, and the bacterial concentration was calculated based on the dilution factor.

$$\frac{\text{ufc}}{\text{mL}} = \frac{\text{number of colonies}}{\text{plated volume}} \cdot \text{DF}$$

Where DF refers to the dilution factor. All the analytical determinations were conducted in triplicate per natural replicate.

2.5. Statistical analysis

A one-way ANOVA was performed to evaluate the effects of experimental conditions, and Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test was used to identify significant differences between treatments. A significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was applied for all tests.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimal nitrogen source

Nitrogen is one of the essential macronutrients that limit microalgae growth. To ensure optimal growth, it is essential to provide a supply of this nutrient in large quantities while ensuring cost-effectiveness for large-scale applications. These factors highlight the importance of efficient nitrogen management for intensive microalgae cultivation. Previous studies have evaluated nitrogen sources such as sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), sodium nitrite (NaNO_2), urea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$), and ammonium chloride (NH_4Cl), in different microalgae species including *Ellipsoidon* sp.²⁷ and *Scenedesmus bijugatus*²⁸. This study aims to identify the optimal nitrogen source for *C. sorokiniana*, given that microalgae have demonstrated variable efficiencies in the assimilation of different nitrogen sources²⁹. To the best of the authors knowledge, this is the first time that a scalable medium is designed for this strain. To address this, agricultural fertilizers were tested as nitrogen sources, including three inorganic compounds (NaNO_3 , NH_4Cl and NaNO_2) and one

organic compound ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$). While it is a standard practice to use both KH_2PO_4 and K_2HPO_4 to maintain buffering capacity, in this case the alkalinity provided by K_2HPO_4 aligned with our design criteria for optimal algal growth (reactors operated at pH 8.0) and carbon utilization (to maximise CO_2 solubilisation and HCO_3^- formation). For this reason, K_2HPO_4 was used as the phosphorus source. The specific culture media composition is detailed in Table 1. Medium A, with NaNO_3 as the nitrogen source, exhibited enhanced growth, reaching a biomass concentration of $4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Figure 1A). This is in line with a previous work, where sodium nitrate was the preferred source a *Chlorella sorokiniana* isolated from a wastewater treatment plant in South Africa ³⁰. In contrast, Medium B, where NH_4Cl constitutes the nitrogen source, the maximum biomass concentration reached was less than $2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, showing lower growth rate. Similar results were obtained in studies conducted on *Chlorella vulgaris*, where the highest biomass productivity was achieved using nitrate and urea, while lower yields were observed with ammonium ³¹. As shown in Figure 1B, a decrease in the Fv/Fm ratio was observed in cultures grown with Medium B (ammonium), which further supports the lower productivity in this culture. The Fv/Fm ratio is a key indicator of photosynthetic efficiency. It is used to assess the maximum quantum yield of photosystem II (PSII) under dark-adapted conditions. In other words, it reflects the maximum potential efficiency of PSII to convert light into chemical energy and is commonly used to assess if the culture is stressed as high irradiance, lack of nutrient, or the accumulation of heavy metals can reduce its value ³². Despite being the most accessible nitrogen form ³³, it resulted in the lowest productivity in this study, with only $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$. This reduced productivity might be caused by the conversion of ammonium to ammonia under certain pH and temperature conditions, which has a toxic effect on cells ^{34–36}. Previous studies observed that concentrations of ammonia higher than $150\text{-}200 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ might be toxic to microalgae ³⁷. In addition, it is possible that the uptake of ammonia reduced the pH of the culture leading to less CO_2 injection and therefore affecting growth.

Moreover, NaNO_2 was tested due to its potential as an alternative nitrogen source (Medium C); however, the use of nitrite resulted in moderate maximum specific growth rates. The biomass productivity ($0.16 \pm 0.01 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) was lower than that achieved using nitrate ($0.29 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) but higher than ammonium ($0.10 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). Moreover, at certain concentrations, nitrite can be toxic to microalgae, inhibiting both photosynthesis and cell growth^{38,39}. The identification of strains that can tolerate nitrite is interesting because this compound can be toxic to other microorganisms⁴⁰, and it could serve as a strategy to avoid or reduce microbial contaminations. As shown in Figure 1C, Medium D ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$) productivity ($0.21 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) was slightly lower than nitrate (Medium A) but higher than ammonium (Medium B) and nitrite (Medium C). The positive effects of urea on biomass production have been documented, including increased dry weight, cell area, and cell count⁴¹. After being absorbed by the cells, urea is converted into ammonium and bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), which can be used as a carbon source for photosynthesis⁴².

Overall, sodium nitrate (Medium A) was identified as the most effective nitrogen source for *C. sorokiniana*, providing the highest biomass production rate ($0.29 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$; $p < 0.05$) and maintaining optimal photosynthetic performance (the Fv/Fm value was higher than 0.6, which is the optimal for most strains). Medium D, formulated using urea also showed potential as a viable nitrogen source ($0.21 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$). On the other hand, ammonium chloride (Medium B) is not recommended due to its low efficiency and the potential risk of ammonia toxicity under cultivation conditions. The use of sodium nitrite (Medium C) also presented potential for producing this strain, but it was not selected for further development due to its lower efficiency compared to sodium nitrate.

3.2. Optimal N:P molar ratio

The N:P molar ratio plays a crucial role in microalgae cultivation, influencing biomass production, nutrient uptake efficiency, and overall metabolic activity. The Redfield ratio (16:1) is widely used as a benchmark for nutrient balance in aquatic ecosystems,

representing the typical molar ratio of N:P in marine environments. However, this ratio does not apply universally. Significant deviations have been reported, with N:P ratios in marine particulate matter ranging from 5 to 34, depending on the local availability of nutrients, environmental conditions, and the specific metabolic requirements of organisms⁴³. These variations underscore the necessity to determine the optimal N:P ratio in controlled cultivation systems tailored to the target organism and production goals. By adjusting this ratio, it is possible to reduce nutrient losses in the exhausted medium. In this study, four different N:P molar ratios, 6:1 (Medium A6), 11:1 (Medium A11), 16:1 (Medium A16), and 21:1 (Medium A21) were evaluated. The Fv/Fm value remained stable across all tested ratios (Figure 2B), indicating that photosynthetic efficiency remained constant despite variations in nutrient balance. This demonstrates that the cells can adapt to changing concentrations of phosphorus with no adverse effects at least on their photosynthetic performance. However, as shown in Figure 2A, the cultures exhibited differences in the biomass concentration reached at the end of the batch phase among the different N:P ratios tested. The 21:1 ratio (Medium A21) was identified as the most efficient, achieving a rate of $0.33 \pm 0.01 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, higher than the productivity observed with the 16:1 ratio (Medium A16). In turn, the 6:1 ratio (Medium A6) yielded the lowest biomass productivity, with values of $0.28 \pm 0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (Figure 2C). Excess phosphorus concentrations at the lower N:P ratios may have led to suboptimal nitrogen uptake, reducing overall productivity. Similar findings were reported in a previous study⁴⁴ with *Nannochloropsis sp.*, where an N:P ratio of 16:1 resulted in excess phosphorus for biomass production, allowing the ratio to be increased to over 32:1 without negatively affecting productivity or composition. However, it has been demonstrated that the optimal N:P molar ratio for biomass production can vary significantly based on specific cultivation and environmental conditions. These results highlight the necessity of tailoring nutrient ratios to species-specific requirements. The observed benefits of a 21:1 N:P ratio provide valuable insights into optimising culture conditions for *C. sorokiniana*.

3.3. Minimisation of nutrient inputs

Reducing nutrient intake is a key strategy for improving the economic and environmental sustainability of microalgae cultivation. Excessive nutrient inputs not only increase operational costs but also lead to resource waste and environmental burdens. This study aimed to assess the impact of gradual nutrient reductions on *C. sorokiniana* productivity. This involved stepwise reductions in nitrogen (NaNO_3) and phosphorous (K_2HPO_4) concentrations, followed by reductions in macronutrients such as magnesium (MgSO_4) and calcium (CaCl_2). The Medium A21 served as a control; the goal was to reduce nutrient inputs without negatively affecting biomass productivity. First, the nitrogen and phosphorous concentrations were reduced by 50% (Medium A21-I). This modification did not affect the biomass productivity, demonstrating that lower nutrient levels can sustain comparable maximum specific growth rates under these conditions (Figure 3C). In a previous work [NO_PRINTED_FORM] ¹¹, it was observed that reducing nitrogen concentration in microalgae culture media not only enhances resource optimisation but also supports growth. Following this initial reduction, the concentration of other macronutrients were gradually reduced. For example, CaCl_2 was reduced by 50% (Medium A21-III) and 75% (Medium A21-VI). Similarly, a reduction of the calcium content did not affect the biomass productivity nor the photosynthetic performance. Similarly, the concentration of magnesium was reduced by 50% (Medium A21-IV) and 75% (Medium A21-VII). Again, the lower content of magnesium showed no adverse effects on the biomass productivity. This aligns with previous studies ⁴⁵ that demonstrated that MgSO_4 could be reduced to $0.34 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ without negatively affecting the growth or stability of *Chlorella vulgaris*. Similarly, it was found that reducing the concentration of CaCl_2 to $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and of MgSO_4 to $0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ did not affect growth in *Haematococcus pluvialis* cultures ⁴⁶.

Micronutrient concentrations were reduced by over 80% (Medium A21-V). As shown in Figure 3B, the Fv/Fm ratio, an indicator of photosynthetic performance, remained stable

within the expected range of 0.65–0.75 for *C. sorokiniana* across all treatments⁴⁷. This suggests that the cultures were not nutrient-stressed. The biomass concentration data, shown in Figure 3A, aligns well with the Fv/Fm value as no significant differences among treatments were observed. In addition to maintaining biomass productivity, reducing nutrient inputs offers significant cost-saving benefits. Commercial culture media formulations often contain excess nutrient concentrations to prevent limitations; this study demonstrates that substantial reductions can be made without compromising performance. It is important to highlight that an optimal culture medium should be designed for each strain as the nutrient requirements are strain dependent. Minimising nutrient inputs also reduces the environmental impact associated with excess nutrient disposal. However, the residual nutrients could potentially be reused by recycling the harvested water in subsequent cultivation cycles, further enhancing sustainability.

3.4. Reutilisation the exhausted culture medium

When reusing the exhausted culture medium during microalgae production, it is important to understand the nutrient dynamics and the potential accumulation of metabolic by-products. For example, the reutilization of the exhausted medium in cultures of *Chlorella vulgaris* is challenging because of the accumulation of extracellular polymeric substances in the culture²¹. In this study, three different recirculation percentages were studied. The effects of recirculating the supernatant at rates of 30%, 50%, and 70% were compared against a control group that received fresh, autoclaved culture medium prepared using the previously optimized composition: 1.25 g·L⁻¹ NaNO₃, 0.12 g·L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄, 0.2 g·L⁻¹ MgSO₄, 0.1 g·L⁻¹ CaCl₂ and 0.005 g·L⁻¹ micronutrients commercial mixture.

Recirculating the supernatant led to a gradual decline in biomass concentration over time (Figure 4). During the batch mode production phase, a maximum biomass concentration of 4 g·L⁻¹ was achieved, indicating that the optimised culture medium effectively supported cell growth under these conditions. During the semi-continuous mode growth

phase, the control culture maintained a biomass concentration above $3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, confirming that regular replenishment with fresh medium sustained productivity. However, cultures with recirculated supernatant exhibited progressively lower biomass concentrations, approaching $2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ at day 29. Higher recirculation rates led to more pronounced reductions ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that certain inhibitory factors accumulate over time, negatively affecting biomass yield. For example, the continuous replenishment of sodium nitrate may lead to sodium accumulation, which can affect osmotic balance and cell physiology. Indeed, osmotic stress led to damages in the oxygen evolving complex and the PSII reaction centre in cultures of *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁴⁸. A similar decline in biomass productivity with *Nannochloropsis sp.* after 16 days of recirculation, despite nutrient replenishment, has been reported⁴⁹. The authors of that study observed that the accumulation of cellular debris and by-products particles contributed to cell aggregation and reduced growth. Similarly, it has been found that high cell densities in *Scenedesmus sp.* cultures, trigger the release of autoinhibitory compounds that are responsible for the cell cycle alteration and reduced overall growth efficiency⁵⁰. To the best of the authors knowledge, this is the first report assessing the effect of culture medium reutilisation in cultures of *C. sorokiniana*. These findings suggest that recirculation strategies should consider not only nutrient replenishment but also the potential accumulation of growth-inhibiting substances that may affect culture performance. Although recirculation was employed to enhance resource efficiency, a slight deterioration in biomass quality was observed. This could be attributed to factors such as increased oxidative stress, nutrient imbalances, or the presence of extracellular metabolites that interfere with normal cellular processes. However, the precise mechanisms underlying this effect remain unclear and require further investigation.

To further understand the effects of recirculating the harvested supernatant, additional analyses were conducted to evaluate changes in the physicochemical and microbiological properties of the culture medium. The assessments focused on microbial

growth, carbon content, turbidity, and viscosity, key parameters that can influence biomass productivity and overall culture stability. Future studies will also evaluate the accumulation of minerals in the recirculated culture as well as their effect on growth. The decline in productivity was correlated with an increase of these parameters. The chemical composition of the medium was affected, as the TOC level increased from 109 mg·L⁻¹ in the fresh medium to 205 mg·L⁻¹ at 70% recirculation ($p < 0.05$). The increase in TOC suggests an accumulation of dissolved organic compounds, probably carbohydrates and proteins released by the cells. Additionally, TIC increased from 103 mg·L⁻¹ in the control culture to 176 mg·L⁻¹ in the culture formulated using 70% of recirculated media ($p < 0.05$). These variations, represented in Figure 5A, indicated a higher accumulation of both organic and inorganic compounds, which may result from cellular excretions, metabolic products, or microbial activity. Such changes could have impacted the overall availability of nutrients and influenced the growth dynamics of *C. sorokiniana*. Other important parameters influenced by recirculation were the viscosity and the turbidity of the media. Viscosity (Figure 5B) increased from 4.6 ± 0.1 mPa·s in the control culture to 5.7 ± 0.1 mPa·s in the cultures being produced using 70% of medium recirculation ($p < 0.05$). Note that the viscosity of water is 1 mPa·s at 20 °C. This increase is likely due to the above-mentioned extracellular polymeric substances produced by microalgae and bacterial communities present in the culture. Viscosity is an important parameter in microalgal cultures as it affects mixing, gas exchange, light exposure and, therefore, cell growth. It might not have a striking effect at the laboratory scale but is crucial in large-scale systems where achieving high mass transfer is challenging. Rheological properties also affect downstream processing technologies including harvesting and dewatering, impacting energetic requirements⁵¹. Similarly, the turbidity showed a marked increase (Figure 5C), rising from 13.7 ± 4.2 NTU to 79.7 ± 4.5 NTU with higher recirculation rates ($p < 0.05$). This suggests an accumulation of suspended particles, including cellular debris and extracellular polymeric substances. Previous work revealed that in a culture of *Scenedesmus sp.* the excretion of organic

substances increased with the growth rate and with the cell concentration⁵². The accumulation was primarily due to the release of growth-associated products. These extracellular components can negatively impact light penetration and overall culture performance. Indeed, increased turbidity has been associated with reduced photosynthetic efficiency previously³⁷. This could partially explain the observed decline in biomass productivity under high recirculation conditions. The higher concentration of organic matter can potentially promote the growth of bacteria. Indeed, the total aerobic mesophylls proliferation was another significant factor affecting culture performance. Their concentration increased from 3.34 log CFU·mL⁻¹ in the control culture to 4.12 log CFU·mL⁻¹ in cultures where 50% and 70% of the supernatant was recirculated ($p < 0.05$). These results are shown in Figure 5D. This finding suggests that recirculation may promote microbial proliferation, potentially affecting culture stability and biomass quality. Similar results have been reported in a previous study with *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, where a high bacterial load in the supernatant was attributed to the recirculation of bacteria and organic matter, which promoted their proliferation⁵³.

Overall, while the reutilisation of the exhausted culture medium can be beneficial for nutrient recycling and cost reduction, it also presents challenges related to culture stability, microbial contamination, and physical alterations of the culture (e.g., turbidity, viscosity). The observed increases in TIC/TOC, viscosity, turbidity, and microbial populations, highlight the need for further optimizing the recirculation strategies. Future studies should focus on mitigating these negative effects, through pre-treatments on the supernatant to enhance biomass yield while maintaining culture integrity.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated that optimising the culture medium is key to enhancing the productivity and sustainability of *Chlorella sorokiniana* production. Sodium nitrate was

identified as the most effective nitrogen source for promoting biomass productivity. Additionally, a N:P molar ratio of 21, higher than the conventional standard, led to higher productivities with lower phosphorus inputs, highlighting the importance of tailoring nutrient ratios to the specific needs of the microalgae. Furthermore, significant reductions in nutrient inputs, including macronutrients and micronutrients, were achieved without affecting growth or photosynthetic efficiency. These findings demonstrate the potential to minimise resource consumption while maintaining productivity. The culture media reuse through recirculation was also tested as a potential strategy to minimise nutrient (and water) requirements. While recirculation reduced water and nutrient consumption, it led to a decline in culture performance at higher recirculation rates. This was attributed to increases in TIC/TOC, viscosity, turbidity, and microbial populations. The accumulation of minerals might have also played a role, although this was not assessed in this study. These results revealed the need for effective pre-treatment approaches to mitigate these effects. Future efforts should focus on optimising medium recirculation practices and evaluating their impact on biochemical composition and biomass quality. Scaling these optimised protocols to industrial systems and assessing their technical and economic feasibility will also be critical to support the transition from laboratory-scale studies to large-scale production.

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Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study available from the corresponding author on reasonable request

Declaration of interests

The authors have no conflict of interests to declare

Author contributions: CRediT

Salinas-Garcia, M.: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal Analysis;
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Table 1. Composition of the culture media

	Medium							
Nutrient*	A	B	C	D	A6	A11	A16	A21
NaNO ₃ (g·L ⁻¹)	2.50	-	-	-	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
NH ₄ Cl (g·L ⁻¹)	-	1.58	-	-	-	-	-	-
NaNO ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-
CH ₄ N ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	0.87	-	-	-	-
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.42	1.15	0.60	0.42	0.32
MgSO ₄ ·H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82
CaCl ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹)**	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Medium							
Nutrient*	A21-I	A21-II	A21-III	A21-IV	A21-V	A21-VI	A21-VII	
NaNO ₃ (g·L ⁻¹)	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25	
NH ₄ Cl (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
NaNO ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
CH ₄ N ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
K ₂ HPO ₄ ·3H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	
MgSO ₄ ·H ₂ O (g·L ⁻¹)	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.41	0.82	0.82	0.20	
CaCl ₂ (g·L ⁻¹)	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.40	0.10	0.40	
Micronutrients (mg·L ⁻¹)**	30.0	10.0	30.0	30.0	5.0	30.0	30.0	

* All the culture media were prepared using commercial fertilisers** Karentol® Mix Super (Kenogard, Barcelona, Spain) is a commercial mixture of micronutrients including boron, copper, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Effect of the nitrogen source on (A) the biomass concentration, (B) Fv/Fm ratio, and (C) biomass productivity of *Chlorella sorokiniana*. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture media is shown in Table 1.

Figure 2. Effect of the molar N:P ratio on (A) the growth, (B) Fv/Fm value, and (C) biomass productivity of *Chlorella sorokiniana*. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture media is shown in Table 1.

Figure 3. Effect of reducing the nutrient concentration on (A) the growth, (B) Fv/Fm value, and (C) biomass productivity of *Chlorella sorokiniana*. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. The composition of the culture media is shown in Table 1.

Figure 4. Effect of water reutilisation on the growth of *Chlorella sorokiniana*. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD.

Figure 5. (A) Total organic carbon, (B) viscosity, (C) turbidity, and (D) total aerobic mesophylls of the exhausted media. Values represent the mean value of three independent determinations \pm SD. Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

